

Motivational Factors among women to become Entrepreneurs: A Qualitative approach

Authors' Details

⁽¹⁾Prof.Dr.Irum rani Laghari- ⁽²⁾Aqsa Sharaf Danwar(MS Student) : Department of Business Administration Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur

Abstract:

Entrepreneurship among women is measured as an important tool in enabling female liberation and empowerment. This paper looks at the literature around women entrepreneurs, focusing on motivating factors for female entrepreneurship in Kairpur and Sukkur cities of Pakistan and to know the reasons on why some women choose to become entrepreneurs. It is important to understand female's motivation to become entrepreneur, because gender inequality still exists specially in developing country like Pakistan and there is a great potential in the Women Entrepreneurship sector.

Keywords: Motivation, Motivational factors, Satisfaction, women Entrepreneurship.

Introduction: Entrepreneurship is the procedure of undertaking actions concerned with identifying and exploiting all the business opportunities while assuming its associated risks. (Iftikhar & Zahir) It is also concerning a type of picky behavior that includes preparation, reorganizing monetary actions and the getting of its danger by inborn power, family background and the profitable environment (Shapero). Female entrepreneurs can be define as those who use their knowledge and resources to create or develop new business opportunities; whether this be casually in a home environment without officially registering their business, hiring office premises or formally via business registration, etc. Who are actively concerned in managing their businesses, are very well responsible in some way for the day-to-day running of their business. (Anwar & Rashid). The purpose of this study is to possibly facilitate the discussion the basic motivating factors as a tool for female entrepreneurship. This paper includes the References from Pakistan and other developing countries have been included as and when appropriate. This study has been conducted in both the urban and rural areas. Although in these areas this is not at the top of a female entrepreneur's list, it is still a goal that these women struggle to achieve (Dzisi, 2008). In Pakistan, like in some developing countries where the income of a single male member is no longer considered as an enough to support the entire family, these women come out of their usual soothe region and join entrepreneurial actions to double the income so they can support their families (Jamali, 2009).

Research Objectives:

The objectives of this study are:

- To examine the motivational factors that could possibly lead women to become entrepreneurs.
- To know the reasons on why some women choose to become entrepreneurs.

- To analyze the influence of each motivational factor among women to become entrepreneur.

Literature Review:

Entrepreneurship is the powerful for the growth of any economy. Female entrepreneurship is, however, still chasing at the back in development when matched to male entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship among women is an idea that women have a propensity to be less involved in the chance of self-employment. It is expected that as a result, intentionally fewer women than men own and manage their own Venture. According to (GEM, 2011), in 2010, 104 million women in around 59 countries, which indicate more than 52% of the world's population and 84% of world GDP, happening and then managed new business ventures. Another 83 million females across those constituencies ran businesses they had opened at least three and a half years ago. Together, these 187 million women add to worldwide entrepreneurship and business possession. Females are most commonly motivated by need to set up their own businesses; a drift that drops as economies grow. Also in the developed countries more women stated about opportunity rather than requirement or necessity as their main motivation. Still, women in less developed economies are very possibly to notice opportunities in their region and have full confidence in their own abilities for entrepreneurship. These females are more likely to know an entrepreneur and plan to start a business, and they have somewhat lower terror of failure compared to other women in economies with much top levels of economic development. Here, fewer women than men intend to start their own venture and more are disheartened by terror of failure. (Hoof & Nandram, 2012)

Economic services have allowed more and more young girls to take up employment. It is out of work accepting, acquaintance to education that the potential source of female entrepreneurs has become known. Women turn

out to be entrepreneurs due to quite a few factors which may be assembled under Pull factors that pass on to the urge to start ventures with a emotion to start a business, while Women incoming business, determined by financial need due to family circumstances are said to be intolerant by Push factors. The motivating forces of can also be subjective by their 'family background'. (Jesurajan & Gnanadhas, 2011)

Entrepreneurial education is one of the sweltering areas for educational and business schools in modern days. Main intention of this education is to bring folks with sufficient awareness, skills and ability that to engage them in entrepreneurial ventures of zone. All these academic institutions are giving many ways specifically women to join entrepreneurial training curriculum. Females are aggravated to look at their opportunities to go into this profession in order to delight many features like autonomy and readiness to be liberal, free, success as a professional, a way to get better wellbeing of their own families and backing the education of their children. Women motivation to get there in entrepreneurship lies with more reasons like admittance to new markets, more monetary options, get business knowledge and skills, information about the backing services and how they can bring in income to their families. The greater part of female starting a business enterprise gets the money from their own savings, family/friends' loans, while men tend to find capital from peripheral sources. This leaning of women not to experience large amount overdue like debts, mutual with their concentration in less capital rigorous service industries, may somewhat account for women opening their business with small amount of capital (ESFC, 1994).(P.R. & M, 2011)

The achievement of entrepreneurs is dependent on own motivation (Urban, 2008) (shane, 2003).Several studies demonstrate motivation distinctions between women and men. For example, Walker and Webster (walker & wabster, 2006) illustrate that there were remarkable differences involving women and men motivations to lope their own venture. Flexible hours, wish to work from residence and the need to sense of balance work and family are main motivations for female entrepreneurs. Many Studies on motivation show a merge results as follows. (Lee, 1997) Lee recommended that women entrepreneurs have a better need for achievement and domination than women that are employed. A study led by Lim et al. (Lim, 2003) tells frequent motivations of becoming entrepreneur like to get full potential, economy motives, to have independence and flexibility and also to turn out to be successful individual. Another study conducted by Orhan and Scott (Orhan & Scott, 2001) shows quite a few types of Female motivations who desire to become entrepreneur: (1) dynastic compliance, (2)

entrepreneurship by chance, (3) no other choice, (4) forced entrepreneurship, (5) natural succession, (6) pure entrepreneur, and (7) knowledgeable entrepreneur. (Sihombing s. O., 2010)

Moore in 2000 developed grouped according to which there are at least 4 behaviors that women will prejudice to develop an entrepreneurial functioning style or work attitude that will sooner or later lead to becoming entrepreneurs: Intentional entrepreneurs: women who always planned to become an entrepreneur, Copreneurs means husband and wife teams, Spiral careerists: women who responded to workplace challenges in entrepreneurial behaviors, Punctuated careerists: women whose alternative to become entrepreneurial was not an clear path. (Parker, 2010)

When approach to women entrepreneurs, it has been argued that money is barely the primary motivating force. Many of them are pragmatic to be alert by the objective of providing good services to their society. They are normally found to be achieving social goals like customer satisfaction, jointly with economic goals. Social issues and problems also act as thrust for women to initiate business. (Publications, 1998). The nervousness for many women is the shared responsibility of work and family and in lots of cases; this creates the need to play a variety of roles like wife, mother and worker/entrepreneur. (Erogul & McCrohan, 2008)

One study of approximately twenty female entrepreneurs found that their key motivation to start their own venture was the desire to be sovereign and independent, the need to accomplish, the want for job satisfaction and economic need (Schwartz, 1976). Need for better life flexibility, seeking challenges, satisfying a long-felt wish or evading from organizational glass ceiling are also amongst the motivation features that direct women to start-up their own businesses (Lee & Rogoff, 1997) (K, Anantharaman, N, & Jayasingam, 2008)

Hypothesis:

HA1: 'Women prefer being independent, making use of the risk taking ability, being competent and utilizing the government or bank loans respectively are the important motivation factors among women'.

HA2: 'Some women tend to become entrepreneur to provide financial stability for the family as well as to get best monetary return for their talent and skills'.

HA3: 'Women need experience change, and they don't usually like to work under anyone because they prefer to have their own working style'.

HA4: ‘One of the main factors among women to become entrepreneur is that they believe in their inner talent to create something innovative, which gives them a Satisfaction’.

H5: ‘Some women fancy leadership roles, authority of being an employer and others aim to attain high social status and earn the respect of people’.

Research Methodology:

The purpose behind this qualitative study is to explore and compare the five main factors (Work, Social, Entrepreneurial, Economic and Individual) that motivates and influence women to come out of their comfort zone and start their own business. The research employed a case study of women in Khairpur and Sindh. Data was collected from over 30 female entrepreneurs, which includes 15 interviews and 20 survey questionnaires, these women are the owners of Beauty salon, Boutique, Accessories shop, Handy crafts etc. including the age of above 20 to 50. All the survey respondents were given 2/3 days’ time to fill the questionnaires. There we over 25 questions in each survey and interview having all factors mentioned. Due to the nature of study which is more of a fact finding, qualitative method has been applied by using NVIVO 10 software by using Word, Text and Matrix queries on the basis of hypothesis.

Results and findings:

Interview and Survey results shows that social core is the main motivational factor among women in this particular area of Pakistan followed by entrepreneurial core. However, Individual, work and Economic core are relatively equal factors in motivating women.

Table 1: Motivation factors

Motivational factors	Females
Social	25.2%
Entrepreneurial	22.9%
Individual	18.38%
Work	18.1%
Economic	16.04%

All the factors influence women positively to start business.

Table 2: Entrepreneurial factor

Age group	Entrepreneurial Factor
20-29	21.4%
30-39	22.83%
40-49	22.74%

Hypothesis 1: women who belongs to age group of 20-29 and 40-49 believe that economic factors which include raising money for own and helping family is a fairly common factor in starting the business, but this factor was more common among women who belongs to age group 30-39 and are mostly married and well settled, they believe that being financially strong is important for their family and children.

Table 3: Economic factor

Age group	Economic Factor
20-29	15.8%
30-39	16.29%
40-49	15.69%

Hypothesis 2: Entrepreneurial core that includes motivation to start a career in a long term perspective is highly effective and risk taking ability to start their own business equally important among the women who belongs to age group 20-29 and 30-39, there were also women among 40-49 who believe that career in owning a business has helped them build their confidence.

Table 4: Individual Factor

Age group	Individual Factor
20-29	19.79%
30-39	17.67%
40-49	17.1%

Hypothesis 3: All the young girls and mature women were highly motivated by individual factor; hence this factor is more common in motivating among women age 20-29. One of the main dimensions is that these ladies desire own lifestyle and work life. They need an

experience change and wanted to enjoy the best luxuries of life. They are more energetic and confident because they feel liberal and free after starting their own business. The feeling of working on own and freely is their motivation. They don't have to work under anyone.

Hypothesis 4: Women among age group of 30-39 and 40-49 feel motivated by this factor more than those in 20-29 age groups. Money is not the sole motivation here, these women believe by helping the society and doing something good for community they feel flattered. The praise they get in return motivates them a lot. They tend to provide good and quality products and services, help their neighbors with their business because in many places they don't have competitors and they are the only business women.

Table 5: Work Factor

Age group	Work Factor
20-29	17.48%
30-39	18.39%
40-49	18.71%

Hypothesis 5: Women among 20-50 equally believe that work factor is their motivation, they tend to have the need to exploit their innate talent and potential in profession, and the motivation to use decision making and problem solving skills in a career, especially in women among 30-39, they need to be creative and more innovative in their business.

Table 6: Social Factor

Age group	Social Factor
20-29	25.52%
30-39	24.82%
40-49	25.75%

Scope of the study:

This study is narrowed to the women entrepreneurs generally engaged in these types of enterprises such as Beauty Salon, Boutique, Accessories shop etc. in district Khairpur and Sukkur Sindh. The personal information on the request of some female entrepreneurs has been kept private.

Conclusion:

All participants stated that they have prepared several things to achieve their aim to become entrepreneurs. Many women believe that Government concessions and loans, all kind of satisfaction, Luxurious life and building a self confidence as time passes, are the biggest motivational sub-factors among women to become entrepreneurs. In many areas Government is providing funds and concessions like Youth support programs, and women appreciate this effort from government and getting facilitated. These women have started their business and running them successfully. Almost all participants stated that to be an entrepreneur is very interested. Each had different interest in specific areas they will involve later. (Sihombing, 2010). They interest in entrepreneurship are also supported by their families. Most of the respondents were confident that they will try to continue being entrepreneur for longer period of time.

Appendix:

1. Text Query:

- 2. Text Query:
 - a. Word cloud:

- b. Word frequency:

Word Frequency Query

yes	objectives	things	freedom	members	else	people	happened	desire	life	point	quality	much	standing	provide	manu	continue	period	friends		
								feel	exactly	time	satisfied	long	educati	custom	finishe	field	take	city	worth	
	rules	starting	community	idea	empowerme	create	materializ						prove	want	hold	lot	accide	expecte	joyir	
								goal	capital	overcome	practice	write								
someone				among	faced	think	employe						main	male	worthy	see	increas	tell	wonde	
	working	motivation	change					profession	observe	family	establis	services				appea	difficu	manysal	love	
				business	deficiencies	place	good						make	others	hopefi					
								supportive	important	products	informal	get				going	beau	gradue	effor	mas
													experie	like	middle					
																learn	came	need	curre	cour

c. Cluster:

3. Motivating factors among women to become entrepreneur: Age group

	A : Economic core	B : Entrepreneurial core	C : Individual core	D : Social core	E : Work core
1 : Person	15.8%	21.4%	19.79%	25.52%	17.48%
2 : Person	16.29%	22.83%	17.67%	24.82%	18.39%
3 : Person	15.69%	22.74%	17.1%	25.75%	18.71%

Motivating factors among women to become entrepreneur: over all female

	A : Economic core	B : Entrepreneurial core	C : Individual core	D : Social core	E : Work core
1 : Person	16.04%	22.29%	18.38%	25.2%	18.1%

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